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Modeling the effect of additives on glass transition and chain dynamics in PHBV

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<p>Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) or PHBV is a prominent biodegradable alternative to replace fossil-based plastics in the food packaging industry. However, several drawbacks still exist, one of the main ones being an increased brittleness over time attributed to secondary crystallization. Nevertheless, previous studies have indicated that the process can be counteracted with suitable additives, such as saccharide molecules. We therefore investigated the effect of seven additives (glucose, fructose, sucrose, lactose, melezitose, ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate) at additive contents 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 % on PHBV with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.</p> <p>The secondary crystallization process could not be directly investigated due to time scale limitations of the MD method. Instead, an elevation in the glass transition temperature T_g and a reduction in chain diffusivity were taken as the foremost indicators of a stabilizing additive effect. The rationale was that increasing T_g above room temperature and thereby decreasing chain mobility, would prevent polymer chains from reorganizing over time, thus inhibiting secondary crystallization. Previous studies with additives had also shown reductions in secondary crystallization, with additive-polymer hydrogen bonding proposed as the underlying mechanism. To investigate the proposal, hydrogen bond patterns were studied to see whether correlations to T_g and chain diffusivity could be found.</p> <p>The screening results indicated that all additives, except ascorbyl palmitate, could increase the T_g. Especially ascorbic acid turned out to be promising. However, the T_g results could not be compared to the diffusion results, as the chain diffusivity turned out to be too slow for a reliable comparison between systems. The capacity of the additives to bridge polymer chains with hydrogen bonds correlated with increases in T_g, although the results suggested that additional mechanisms also contribute. The additive sizes also mattered, as bulkier additives caused larger elevating effects on T_g in general.</p> <p>The thesis presents both an overview of methodological issues rising when trying to rank additives based on their effect on T_g, as well as the additive screening results. Further investigations can then be performed on the most promising additives on the basis of the screening. The thesis also gives guidelines for additive structures to consider in future PHBV based material formulations.</p>		
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1. Introduction

Due to the many beneficial properties of plastics, such as being flexible, durable as well as inexpensive to produce, their application has been increasing yearly in every aspect of life and technology [1]. Plastics usage encompasses almost every sector from building construction and health care to households and everyday disposables [1]. It has been estimated that the total amount of plastics produced between years 1950 and 2019 was an astonishing 8100 Mt and the production rate is increasing every year [1]. The drawback of this ever accelerating rate of plastics production is that none of the commonly used plastics today are biodegradable, which leads to their accumulation in either landfills or the natural environment rather quickly [1]. Especially the largest market for plastics, which is packaging, has been the main contributor in increasing plastics share in municipal solid waste (by mass) from less than 1 % in 1960 to more than 10 % by 2005 in middle and high income countries [2]. Plastic debris has also been found in every ocean, with an estimated 4 to 12 Mt of plastics entering the oceans only in 2010 [2]. Increasing evidence also indicates that microplastics formed from plastic waste may have harmful effects on animal species, including humans [3].

These increasingly widespread and difficult environmental problems, together with the potentially hazardous effects of microplastics, has led researchers to search for alternative solutions. Many promising biodegradable polymers have been investigated, such as polylactic acid (PLA), polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT), polybutylene succinate (PBS), as well as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) [4]. Among the many promising alternatives, the PHA copolymer poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) or PHBV, has gained interest due to properties that in many ways resemble those of traditional fossil-based plastics [5].

A common challenge with biodegradable polymers is how to make the material preserve its beneficial properties, and still have it decay naturally once it has served its purpose. Usually material stability and biodegradability are things that oppose each other. As such, also PHBV has its limitations. It is known to become more brittle over time due to mechanisms attributed to secondary crystallization, as well as a stiffening

of the amorphous material fractions [6]. Nevertheless, previous research has also shown that the process can be altered by blending PHBV with certain additives such as saccharide molecules [7]. Based on these previous observations, the thesis investigated the effect of blending PHBV with seven different additives at varying additive contents with the help of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. The additives chosen were all non-toxic, as well as biodegradable, and included the monosaccharides glucose and fructose, the disaccharides sucrose and lactose and the trisaccharide melezitose. The effect of ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate was also investigated. The idea was to scan various polymer-additive blends with simulations to study how additives affect the physical aging process, that is, embrittlement due to secondary crystallization, when PHBV is stored at room temperature. The additive effect on PHBV was determined based on results from glass transition and diffusion analysis. The rationale was that reducing chain mobility with additives would prevent polymer chains from reorganizing, thus inhibiting secondary crystallization. Hydrogen bonding patterns were also investigated to see whether increased material stability could be attributed to additive-polymer hydrogen bonding. The research was performed as a part of the Horizon Europe ViSS* project that investigates the potential of PHBV-based food packaging scaled up to industrial level. The computational screening formed a basis for the development of new material formulations.

The thesis is structured as follows. Chapter two introduces the reader to polymers and their semicrystalline state. It also covers the glass transition phenomenon and explains how it inhibits polymer chain mobility and consequently secondary crystallization. The chapter also summarizes the benefits and limitations of PHBV, and also contains an overview of additives that can potentially be used to improve upon its limitations. The third chapter introduces the computational method of molecular dynamics simulations, presents the used PHBV and additive models and also contains a summary of the simulation setup and protocol. The fourth chapter presents the analysis methodology used for glass transition, diffusion and hydrogen bonding. The methodological findings and the results from the additive screening are then presented in chapter five along with a discussion of their meaning. The thesis ends with a conclusion of the most important findings in chapter six.

*For more information visit webpage: <https://viss-project.eu/>

2. Theoretical background

The chapter first introduces the reader to polymers, their semicrystalline state and the glass transition. This is the focus of section 2.1. It highlights the metastable nature of semicrystalline polymers, why their properties may change over time, and also possible mechanisms to stabilize them. In section 2.2 PHBV is presented as a promising alternative to fossil-based plastics. Drawbacks are also discussed and a focus is on embrittlement due to secondary crystallization. The chapter ends with reviews of studies showing that secondary crystallization can be inhibited with additives. The studies are presented in section 2.3.

2.1 Polymers, their semicrystalline state and the glass transition

Polymers form an abundant class of materials that can be found almost everywhere in nature and the industry [8]. Examples of polymer materials include cellulose, silk, hair, DNA as well as various plastics such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) [8]. Polymers consist of large chain-like macromolecules that are made of repeating units bonded to each other by covalent bonds [9]. An example is the aforementioned PP, which consists of the repeating unit $[\text{C}_3\text{H}_6]_n$ bonded thousands of times ($n > 1000$) to form a larger macromolecule [9]. The primary structure, that is, the repeating units and their sequence, largely determines the geometry and the properties of the chain. A single chain may consist of only one kind of repeating unit (homopolymer) or be built of many distinct ones (copolymer) [9]. Figure 2.1 shows a linear copolymer consisting of two repeating units. Some polymer chains have repeating units that induce specific chain stereostructures, either due to tacticity or *cis-trans* isomerism [9]. A particular configuration cannot change without breaking primary bonds. On the other hand, some polymer chains have repeating units that make them exhibit flexible backbones, meaning the chains can take on a huge number of different geometrical shapes [9]. A specific chain shape is referred to as a particular chain conformation. The chain length also plays an important role in determining polymer properties. Many properties such

as melting temperature, fracture toughness and Young's modulus increase with molar mass, with constant values approached in the high molar mass regions [9]. The chains interact with each other through weaker secondary bonds, and these interactions are mainly attributed to van der Waals and hydrogen bonding [10]. Melting and crystallization involve the rupture or establishment of a great many secondary bonds [9].

Figure 2.1: Schematic figure of a linear copolymer. It contains two different repeat units A and B that are linked together with covalent bonds to form a polymer chain.

Many polymers are semi-crystalline materials, meaning they form both crystalline and amorphous regions when cooled below their melting temperature [11]. Crystallization of polymers is a process associated with partial alignment of the chains, where chains are folded together forming ordered regions called lamellae. These lamellae compose larger spheroidal structures named spherulites [11]. The single lamellar crystals are roughly 10 nm thick platelets, whereas the size of the spherulites ranges from several hundreds of nanometers even up to some centimeters [11]. The lamellae are separated by amorphous chain regions [11]. Figure 2.2 shows a schematic overview of both the small and large scale structures.

The crystallization process begins when parts of adjacent chains align sufficiently to bond with long range interactions [11]. This can happen once the thermal energy is low enough [11]. The growth of these crystallites is then largely determined by the temperature and time of crystallization, that is, the thermal history [11]. For example, higher temperatures increase chain mobility and thus speed up chain conformation sampling needed to find sufficient chain alignment, but higher thermal energies may also increase the breakdown of initiated crystallites [11]. Polymer materials are often processed as melts at high temperatures, and different cooling rates after melt processing impacts the crystallization outcome, with lower cooling rates resulting in more crystalline regions immediately upon cooling [12]. As such, polymer crystallization is a kinetically controlled process, and unlike for small molecules, the thermal history largely determines the final outcome [11]. The initial crystallization process stops once all crystallizable units have been added to the lamellar stacks in the available timescale of the experiment. This process is called primary crystallization.

Figure 2.2: Schematic figure of a spherulite together with its nanoscale structure. The figure is reproduced with permission from Springer Nature (SNCSC) under license number 5971930013282: Wang, A., Chen, C., Liao, L. et al. *Enhanced β -Phase in Direct Ink Writing PVDF Thin Films by Intercalation of Graphene*. *J Inorg Organomet Polym*, 30, 1497–1502 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10904-019-01310-0>

The amorphous regions, separating the crystal lamellae, consist of all chain segments that have either not been able to interact with nucleation sites or join the growing lamellae [11]. Instead, they have been pushed away by chain segments that could be stretched and thus incorporated into the growing crystals. The rejected segments typically contain end-groups, stereo defects, and chemical perturbations such as co-units or short chain branches that oppose optimal chain alignment [11]. The chain parts in the amorphous regions are disorganized, adopting random coil conformations, and therefore lack the long-range order seen for lamellae.

Over larger timescales, ranging from minutes to months, some semi-crystalline polymers may show significant increases in crystallinity [11]. This slow but steady process is separate from the initial crystallization and is thus denoted secondary crystallization [11]. The mechanism for the increase is that the mobile amorphous regions over time find ways to reorganize, thus eventually thickening the already existing lamellae or forming smaller crystallites between them [11]. The build up of smaller lamellae between the primary stack as well as the lamellar thickening are dependent on the amount of crystallizable units in the amorphous phase as well as the storage temperatures. Figure 2.3 shows an example of how the crystallization process can proceed by gradually lowering the temperature. Secondary crystallization may alter material properties significantly, for instance during storage, by making polymers more brittle and thus prone to breaking [7].

Figure 2.3: Schematic figure of secondary crystallization, focusing on the crystal lamellae. After initial crystallization at temperature T_0 , further crystallization may occur at later times if the temperature is consequently lowered to first T_1 and then to T_2 . As can be seen, the secondary lamellae grow thinner than the primary stack.

Below the melting temperature, polymers can exist in either rubbery or glassy states depending on whether they are above or below their material specific glass transition temperature T_g [13]. Above T_g the amorphous fractions are mobile and can reorganize, whereas below it, the amorphous fractions immobilize. The reduction in chain mobility at T_g is known to inhibit secondary crystallization. The glass transition has many features in common with second-order phase transitions as for example volume and enthalpy are continuous functions through the transition, but their temperature derivatives, the thermal expansion coefficient and the specific heat, change in a discontinuous manner [13]. Figure 2.4 shows how the temperature derivative of density shows a discontinuity at T_g . However, the glass transition is not considered a true phase transition, despite many seeming similarities. It is heavily affected by the time scale of the experiment, such as the cooling rate (see Figure 2.4), and is thus considered a kinetic phenomenon [14]. The transition can be understood as follows. The relaxation time associated with conformational changes of segments in polymer chains follow the Vogel-Fulcher-Tammann (VFT) equation [14].

$$\tau = \tau_0 e^{DT_0/(T-T_0)} \quad (2.1)$$

In equation 2.1, τ_0 represents the high temperature limiting segmental relaxation time and the parameter D is the fragility parameter, quantifying the degree to which relaxation is non-Arrhenius [[15],[16]]. The T_0 parameter, known as the Vogel-Fulcher-Tammann temperature, is the finite temperature at which the relaxation time approaches infinity. At the high temperature limit the VFT equation approaches a

simple Arrhenius form. However, as the temperature is decreased, the relaxation time becomes comparable to the time scale of the experiment at T_g , and this causes the system to fall out of equilibrium with respect to its conformational degrees of freedom [14]. The polymer chains may thus enter conformations where they are stuck at local energy minima in an experimental time scale, leaving the chains in kinetic traps. The T_0 temperature can be thought of as the theoretical low temperature limit for the T_g occurring for infinitesimal quench speeds, which implies that all experimentally observed glass transitions take place at a slightly higher temperature depending on the cooling rate [14]. The VFT equation can be used to relate relaxational processes at different temperatures. In this thesis an equivalent form of the VFT equation, called the William-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation, containing an explicit reference to the glass transition temperature, was used to relate the time scales between simulation and experiment [[15], [16]].

Figure 2.4: Schematic of linear cooling of a polymer showing density as a function of temperature. Crystallization begins after cooling below melting temperature T_m . A discontinuous change in temperature derivatives at the glass transitions can also be observed. T_g^1 corresponds to a faster cooling rate, whereas T_g^2 corresponds to a slower one, highlighting the kinetic nature of the glass transition.

2.2 Polyhydroxyalkanoates and PHBV

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are naturally occurring polyesters accumulated via fermentation processes by microorganisms, such as various bacteria, in the presence of nutrient deficient conditions with an excess carbon source [17]. They are formed from

hydroxyalkanoic acids, such as 3-hydroxybutyric acid and 3-hydroxyvaleric acid, and are a class of biomaterials with biocompatibility, biodegradability as well as tunable mechanical properties [17]. The microorganisms store the cultivated PHAs as small granules, which later serve as energy and carbon reserves [18] (Figure 2.5). Over 90 percent of the dry cell weight can consist of these granules [18]. Depending on the microorganism and the cultivating conditions, many different homo and copolymers with differing repeating units can be obtained [4]. So far more than 150 different PHA monomers have been discovered [19]. Different PHAs can already be found in many fields that demand biodegradability or biocompatibility, such as the packaging industry in the form of bags, cutlery, utensils and cups, as well as the medical field in the form of sutures and drug controlled carriers [17]. The most investigated PHA has been poly-3-hydroxybutyrate (PHB) and its copolymers [17]. Besides non-toxicity and biodegradability, PHB shows high tensile strength similar to that of PP and its gas barrier properties even exceed those of PP and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [17]. However, its brittleness, stiffness, and high processing temperatures needed for material engineering have limited its large scale application [17]. The limitations can be overcome by copolymerizing the 3HB repeating units with other PHA monomers [17]. A promising copolymer has turned out to be PHBV or poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate). Table 2.1 shows a comparison between a group of properties of PP, the homopolymer PHB and the copolymer PHBV.

Figure 2.5: PHBV accumulated as granules inside the bacterium *C. glutamicum* is shown. The left figure shows the granules in the μm scale, whereas the right one is a magnification shown in the nm scale. The figure is reused and modified (upper half cropped away) under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>): Ma, W., Wang, J., Li, Y. et al. *Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) co-produced with l-isoleucine in Corynebacterium glutamicum WM001*. *Microb Cell Fact* 17, 93 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-018-0942-7>

PHBV is obtained by copolymerization of 3-hydroxybutyric acid and 3-hydroxyvaleric acid. This results in a copolymer with two repeating units,

3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) and 3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV). The structural formula of PHBV is shown in Figure 2.6. Its properties depend on the amount of 3HV content, and finding the optimal range for the target application is thus important. Table 2.2 shows the impact of 3HV content on PHBV properties. As can be seen 3HV units lower the melting temperature, making the material easier to handle as lower temperatures are needed in production. Increasing the 3HV content also increases material toughness, improves the elongation at break and lowers the crystallinity, making PHBV flexible and thus less brittle than the homopolymer (PHB) [17]. Most practical applications would require a minimum 3HV content of 10–20 % mol [17].

Figure 2.6: Structural formula of PHBV. It contains m number of 3HB units copolymerized with n number of 3HV units.

Property	PP	PHB	PHBV
M_w [10^5 g/mol]	2.2–7	1–8	3
ρ [kg/dm^3]	0.905	1.25	1.2
T_m [K]	449	444–455	*348–445
T_g [K]	263	277–283	*260–281
χ^c [%]	70	80	*55–70
Tensile strength (MPa)	38	40	*25–30
Elongation (%)	400	6	8–1200*
Elastic modulus (GPa)	1.7	3.5	2.9 (3%3HV) 0.7 (25%3HV)
Solvent resistance	Yes	No	No
Biodegradability	No	Yes	Yes

Table 2.1: Comparison between properties of fossil-based PP and the biodegradable alternatives PHB and PHBV (3HV conc. 4–95%) [[17][20]]. M_w denotes molar mass, ρ denotes material density and χ^c denotes crystallinity index. The star (*) in the PHBV column indicates a higher 3HV content.

On the other hand, increasing 3HV content decreases the glass transition temperature and the relatively high degree of noncrystalline fractions make PHBV undergo changes in its structure at room temperature. In other words, on storage at ambient conditions, the beneficial properties of PHBV deteriorate over time. This process is attributed to secondary crystallization, as well as a stiffening of the

3HV%	T_m (K)	T_g (K)	Tens. strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Elastic mod. (GPa)
0 (PHB)	448–453	277–282	40–45	4–5	3.5–3.8
3	443	–	38	–	2.9
11	430	275	38	5	3.7
20	387–418	268–274	20–32	27–50	0.8–1.9
28	375	265	32	700	1.5
34	370	264	18	970	1.2

Table 2.2: Properties of PHBV as a function of 3HV content. Changing the 3HV/3HB ratio alters the material properties and thus the ratio can be optimized for a specific application [21].

amorphous material fractions [6]. Secondary crystallization increases the degree of crystallinity and embrittlement ensues, leading to a significant reduction in ductility [7]. The process remains active for weeks to months, and possibly even years. Possible ways to mitigate the negative effects of secondary crystallization are to either increase the glass transition temperature of PHBV above room temperature, which would immobilize the amorphous fractions at ambient conditions, or to enhance primary crystallization. This thesis work focuses on the former solution. For this purpose, blending small molecules with PHBV has turned out to be promising [7].

2.3 Modifying polymer properties with additives

Synthetic polymers are typically accompanied by various smaller molecules called additives in order to alter the original material properties in beneficial ways [22]. Common polymers in everyday use such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyurethane (PUR) and polyvinyl acetate (PVA) all contain small molecules added for various engineering purposes [22]. These can be to inhibit oxidation by the addition of antioxidants, to facilitate melt flow by addition of lubricants and also to improve material stability by affecting chain movement with the addition of anti-plasticizers [22]. For this thesis, the important additives are the anti-plasticizers. They increase viscosity and material strength and may also increase the glass transition temperature [22].

The addition of certain small molecules to both PHB and PHBV has been shown to decrease the rate and extent of secondary crystallization [[7],[23]]. The observed reduction has been attributed to greater steric hindrances, as well as more interacting groups being present [7]. In other words, bulky and sticky additives can prevent the polymer chains from attaining the regular conformations needed for secondary

crystallization to proceed. Especially intermolecular hydrogen bonding has been indicated as a promising approach for enhancing material properties [7]. The focus of blending additives with PHB and its copolymers has therefore been the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds between hydroxy groups in the additive and the carbonyl groups of PHB [23]. It is assumed that these interactions physically cross-link adjacent polymer chains in the amorphous phase through the additives [23]. Figure 2.7 shows a schematic overview of the physical bridging that is believed to partially be behind the reduced rates in secondary crystallization.

Figure 2.7: Schematic presentation of glucose molecules physically bridging two adjacent PHBV chains with hydrogen bonds. The working hypothesis is that such cross-links prevents the amorphous fractions from reorganizing over time, thus inhibiting secondary crystallization. R denotes a one or two carbon atom side chain, depending on the repeating unit (3HB vs 3HV).

Molecules such as Bisphenyl A (BPA) and 4,4-thiodiphenol (TDP) that contain two hydroxy groups, are capable of hydrogen bonding with nearby carbonyl groups present in PHB [[7],[23]]. The groups are separated by two bulky phenyl rings, which limits the approach of polymer chains, by acting as chain defects. This results in a reduction in both primary and secondary crystallization [[7],[23]]. However, both BPA and TDP have turned out to be potent endocrine disruptors and they cannot be used in food packaging anymore [[7],[23]]. Instead, other non-toxic additive alternatives have been considered. Starch, a large polymer consisting of glucose units, displays similar functional groups as BPA, but is non-toxic to the body. Previous studies have revealed that blending starch with PHB effectively decreases crystallinity and improves thermal stability [7]. However, the high melting point of starch in comparison to the degradation temperature of PHB, limits the potential for miscibility upon blending. In other words, material processing has to be carried out below the melting point of starch, resulting in the incorporation of starch granules of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in size [7]. This, in turn, leads to a loss of the beneficial mechanical properties of PHB, with decreases observed in both tensile strength and elongation at break [7]. As starch is a relatively large molecule, the incorporation of smaller saccharides with melting points below

that of PHBV has been proposed as potential property modifiers. A 2019 study by Jenkins et al. [7] found that saccharides such as glucose, fructose, maltose and melezitose indeed could reduce the rate of secondary crystallization in PHBV, as well as lower the processing temperatures needed for handling the material. The conclusion of the study was that larger saccharides had greater inhibiting effects on secondary crystallization.

As empirical evidence suggested that saccharide molecules could have inhibiting effects on secondary crystallization, they were considered in this thesis work as the primary additive type. Ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate were also later added to the list of additives to be investigated. As was mentioned in the introductory chapter, the objective of the present study was to find suitable additives to mitigate PHBV physical aging, together with optimal loadings, and also to look for a mechanistic explanation of the additive effects. As experimental scanning through a large pool of additives at various loadings is a slow and costly process, computer simulations were utilized to speed up the research.

3. Computational methods

The chapter starts with a brief presentation of the molecular dynamics method in section 3.1. The next section 3.2, presents the atomistic models for both PHBV and the additives. The last section 3.3 contains an overview of the simulation protocol and also contains details of the simulation setup.

3.1 Molecular dynamics

Molecular dynamics (MD) is a computer simulation method used to predict the time evolution of complex molecular systems that cannot be solved analytically [24]. MD simulations are usually used to either narrow the gap between experiment and theory in domains where direct experiments are not currently possible, or to predict various material properties that would otherwise be cumbersome to obtain through experiments alone [24]. The basic idea is that atoms are modeled as point particles, which are propagated in time by solving a classical equation of motion, such as Newton's second law shown in equation 3.1, with finite difference methods [25]:

$$\mathbf{f}_i = -\nabla_i V(\{\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N\}) = m_i \mathbf{a}_i \quad (3.1)$$

In other words, given a potential V that is typically dependent on all N atom coordinates in the system, the acceleration \mathbf{a}_i of a single atom at position \mathbf{r}_i , is calculated from the gradient of the potential divided by the atom mass m_i , according to equation 3.1. The acceleration is calculated for each atom present in the system and the atom positions and velocities are then updated, for example, using the velocity-Verlet algorithm, defined below [25].

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t) = \mathbf{v}_i(t) + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{a}_i(t)\delta t \quad (3.2)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t + \delta t) = \mathbf{r}_i(t) + \mathbf{v}_i(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t)\delta t \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t_0 + \delta t) = \mathbf{v}_i(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t) + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{a}_i(t_0 + \delta t)\delta t \quad (3.4)$$

The first step (3.2) estimates the velocities at an intermediate time $t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t$, given velocities and accelerations at time t , and these mid-step velocities are then used to update the coordinates from time t to $t + \delta t$ (step 3.3). After that, a force evaluation is carried out with equation 3.1 to give the acceleration at time $t + \delta t$ needed for step 3.4, which completes the evolution of the velocities [25]. The velocity-Verlet algorithm is found to be numerically stable, time reversible and has excellent energy conserving properties even at larger time steps [25]. The time step δt is a user-defined parameter that specifies the numerical accuracy of the solution. A smaller time step increases the accuracy but comes with a computational cost. The time step should be chosen so that decreasing it further would not change the outcome (statistics) of the simulation [25].

As the dynamics of the system is governed by the potential V , it is crucial that it models the interatomic forces as accurately as possible [26]. Different functional forms can be used depending on the system under consideration. The potential together with its set of parameters are often referred to as a force field, with common examples including the AMBER and CHARMM family of force fields [27]. The force field parameters are typically obtained from experimental data or derived using quantum mechanical calculations [24]. An example of a typical potential form is shown below [24]:

$$V = \underbrace{V_{\text{bond}} + V_{\text{angle}} + V_{\text{dihedral}}}_{\text{Bonded interactions}} + \underbrace{V_{\text{van der Waals}} + V_{\text{Coulomb}}}_{\text{Non-bonded interactions}} \quad (3.5)$$

As can be seen in 3.5 the functional form consists of two parts. The bonded interactions in non-reactive force fields are unbreakable, and are used to describe the ionic and covalent bonds of molecules [24]. The bonded interactions are typically modeled with harmonic forces, which allow the atoms in molecules to wiggle, bend and rotate around specified equilibrium values [24]. The non-bonded interactions, on the other hand, model the long range intra and intermolecular interactions that consist of van der Waals and Coulombic contributions [24]. The van der Waals term models the attractive dispersion and steric repulsion between atoms, which are typically modeled with the Lennard-Jones potential. If there exist charge distributions, a Coulombic term must be added as well. For instance, otherwise neutral molecules may have charge distributions due to differing electron affinity of atoms constituting the molecules. To account for this, the concept of partial charge is used. The idea is that the atoms are set to have different charges in order to reproduce the electrostatic potential surrounding the molecules. The assignment of partial charges is made based on quantum mechanical calculations [24].

The most time consuming part of a simulation is calculating the forces between atoms interacting through long range interactions [24]. The number of pairwise interactions increases rapidly as the number of atoms in the system increases, leading to a huge number of computations at each time step. This is problematic for practical purposes. However, fortunately for the van der Waals interaction, the interaction strength decreases fast with distance making it sufficiently weak to be approximated to zero after a specific cutoff distance [24]. Thus, only atoms inside the specified cutoff must be taken into consideration when calculating the interactions. To avoid an abrupt truncation of the potential once atoms passes the cutoff, long range potentials are typically adjusted to zero by smoothly reshaping the original potential. However, for the Columbic interaction the cutoff procedure cannot be used, as it does not decay fast enough. In order to handle it efficiently, other techniques have been developed instead, one of the most widely used implementation being the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method [26].

An important concept in MD is the simulation of ensembles familiar from statistical mechanics. Almost all simulations are carried out keeping one or more thermodynamic variables, such as temperature or volume constant, thereby defining a particular ensemble [28]. The idea is to mimic experimental conditions as closely as possible, thus making the simulations comparable to experiments. Two commonly used ensembles are the canonical ensemble and the isothermal-isobaric ensemble [28]. In the former the volume, particle number and temperature are kept constant, whereas in the latter the pressure, particle number and temperature are kept constant [28]. Algorithms have been developed to mimic the thermodynamic ensembles by altering the system dynamics. All algorithms involve modifying the equations of motion, either by introducing stochastic terms or by adding deterministic effects through additional dynamical variables or constraints [25]. Popular temperature control methods are the Berendsen and Nosé-Hoover thermostats, whereas pressure control is often handled with the Berendsen or Parrinello-Rahman barostats [[25],[29]]. Besides studying MD systems in equilibrium conditions, non-equilibrium processes, such as constant-rate heating and cooling, can also be studied. The idea is to change the temperature at a constant rate to see how the system reacts to such environmental changes. Both equilibrium and non-equilibrium simulations were carried out during the thesis work. Isothermal-isobaric simulations were performed to obtain diffusion and hydrogen bonding data, whereas simulated cooling was performed to estimate the glass transition temperatures.

3.2 Atomistic models of PHBV-additive blends

The PHBV polymer chains were created as 100 repeat unit long random sequences of 3HB and 3HV dimers containing an 3HV content of 15 %. The chain production included the following steps: (1) the monomer sequence along each chain was determined through random sampling, (2) molecular models of the individual chains were created in random coil conformations, and (3) an energy minimization was carried out for each chain with respect to the atomic coordinates. An example of a PHBV chain can be seen in Figure 3.1. The chosen polymerization degree of 100 gave the chains a contour length of roughly 30 nm. The chain length was motivated by the following considerations: (1) The chains were still considered short enough to not have an excessive amount of self-interactions over the periodic boundaries, (2) the chains were long enough for the glass transition temperature to be near its limiting value, (3) the bulk polymer systems could still be equilibrated at a high temperature with reasonable computational resources. The interatomic forces for PHBV were modeled with the GAFF force field (Wang et al. 2005) with optimized partial charges obtained with the default HF/6-31G + RESP approach. The charge assignments were tested by comparing simulated predictions for PHBV density and glass transition temperature against literature values.

Figure 3.1: Left: An example of a PHBV chain containing 100 randomly distributed 3HB and 3HV block dimers (15% 3HV content). Right: Distribution of glucose molecules within the simulation domains at 2, 6 and 10 % loadings. The polymer chains are hidden for illustrative purposes.

The additives chosen to be studied were the monosaccharides glucose and fructose, the disaccharides sucrose and lactose, the trisaccharide melezitose, as well as ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate. The additives were required to be non-toxic and biodegradable, so that they would be compatible with food packaging applications. As previously stated, saccharide molecules had been observed to reduce the rate and extent of secondary crystallization (Jenkins et al. [7]). Ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate were included in the study, as they were expected to have potential antioxidant effects, and also due to them sharing similar chemical properties with the saccharides. The additive contents 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 % were considered. This is a typical range used in polymer engineering. The additive content was defined as the total additive mass divided by the polymer mass in the system. Figure 3.1 shows simulation domains with glucose molecules uniformly dispersed in the system at additive contents 2, 6 and 10 %. The polymer chains are hidden for increased clarity.

Additive	M (g/mol)	2	4	6	8	10 %
Glucose	180.156	95	191	287	383	478
Fructose	180.156	95	191	287	383	478
Sucrose	342.297	50	100	151	201	252
Lactose	342.297	50	100	151	201	252
Melezitose	504.438	34	68	102	136	171
Ascorbic acid	176.124	97	195	293	391	489
Ascorbyl palmitate	414.539	41	83	124	166	208

Table 3.1: Number of additive molecules corresponding to additive contents of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 %. The additive molar masses are also shown for reference.

All saccharides were modeled with the GLYCAM force field (Kirschner et al. 2008), whereas ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate were modeled with GAFF. To enable hybrid GLYCAM-GAFF models in the GROMACS simulation engine, inline parameters were written for the 1-4 non-bonded interactions in the GLYCAM topologies. The considered additive species and their isomeric forms, molar masses, loadings and other key properties are summarized in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. Figure 3.2 shows the chemical structures of the additives.

3.3 Simulation protocol and setup

The polymer-additive systems were created by first randomly distributing the collection of polymer chains into a simulation domain to form a low-density system.

Figure 3.2: Chemical structures of the investigated additives.

Additive (chemical formula)	Isomerism (glycosidic linkage)	T_g (K)	Donors	Acceptors
Glucose ($C_6H_{12}O_6$)	β -D-glucopyranose	304	5	6
Fructose ($C_6H_{12}O_6$)	β -D-fructofuranose	278	5	6
Sucrose ($C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$)	α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-fructofuranoside	335	8	11
Lactose ($C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$)	β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside	374	8	11
Melezitose ($C_{18}H_{32}O_{16}$)	α -D-glucopyranosyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-fructofuranoside	-	11	16
Ascorbic acid ($C_6H_8O_6$)	L-ascorbic acid	-	4	6
Ascorbyl palmitate ($C_{22}H_{38}O_7$)	-	-	3	7

Table 3.2: Some key properties of the investigated additives, including the glass transition temperatures [30], the additive isomerisms, as well as the number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors.

The amorphous model was considered to be an acceptable approximation of the interlamellar mobile amorphous fraction (MAF) in semicrystalline PHBV, which is the fraction involved in secondary crystallization. The ParmEd (Shirts et al. 2017), MBuild (Klein et al. 2016), Foyer (Klein et al. 2019), OpenMM (Eastman et al. 2012), OpenBabel (O’Boyle et al. 2011) and doGlycans (Danne et al. 2017) software tools were used when building the atomistic models, including the topologies and coordinates. Secondly, additives were randomly distributed into the low-density blends at the given additive contents. A condensed-phase polymer-additive melt was then created, by consecutive compression (1 ns at 300 K, 1 atm) and heating (linear

heating from 300 to 700 K in 1 ns, 1 atm). The systems were equilibrated at the artificially high temperature of 700 K and 1 atm external pressure. The extreme temperature allowed for faster relaxation of chain conformations and was possible to use as the force fields where non-reactive and thus not allowing polymer degradation. A similar relaxation procedure had been used in a previous study by Bejagam et al [31]. The equilibration was performed for 150 ns, and five (5) independent starting configurations were chosen for each polymer-additive system at time stamps 110 ns, 120 ns, 130 ns, 140 ns and 150 ns in order to obtain statistics for the glass transition analyses. Proper equilibration of the polymer melt was checked with mean square internal distance (MSID) analysis of the chain conformations, which showed convergence after approximately 100 ns.

Figure 3.3: Simulation protocol used in this work. Linear cooling simulations were used for the glass transition analysis, whereas the isothermal simulations were used for hydrogen bonding and diffusivity analysis.

Linear cooling simulations, used for glass transition prediction, were then carried out (first for the neat polymer to verify the method and later for all systems) from 700 to 100 K. Constant cooling rates of 600, 300, 150, 60, 30, 15 and 6 K/ns were used, except for systems containing ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate, for which the slowest quench was omitted. In other words, only a single additive investigation contained six to seven (6–7) quenches and each quench had five (5) glass transition estimates obtained from the initial configurations. Further 800 ns isothermal-isobaric simulations were carried out at 370 K temperature and 1 atm pressure, starting from the 370 K configuration obtained using the 15 K/ns cooling rate. Additive loadings of 2, 6 and 10 % were considered for all PHBV-additive systems. The results were used to obtain hydrogen bonding statistics and diffusivity estimates for the polymer chains and the additive species.

All simulations were carried out using GROMACS version 2024.2. The temperature was controlled with the v-rescale thermostat (Bussi et al. 2007) and a time constant of 1 ps. The pressure was set to 1 atm with the c-rescale barostat (Bernetti and Bussi 2020) and a time constant of 5 ps. The integrator was the velocity-Verlet algorithm and the time step was set to 2 fs. The LINCS (Hess et al. 1997) algorithm was used to constrain the vibrations of bonds involving hydrogen. The long range interactions were handled with the potential-shift cut-off scheme for the van der Waals interactions, and the particle mesh Ewald (PME) scheme for the Coulombic interactions.

4. Analysis methodology

The chapter presents the analysis methodology used when analyzing the molecular trajectories. Section 4.1 covers the glass transition estimation and diffusion analysis. It may be illuminating to read it together with section 5.1 of the results chapter, where the methodological results are presented. The next section 4.2 then presents the methodology used to obtain hydrogen bonding statistics.

4.1 Glass transition estimation and diffusivity

A common method by which to determine the glass transition temperature in MD is to fit tangents to density-temperature $\rho(T)$ data in the linear regions at both high and low temperatures, and then report the intersection as the estimated T_g value [32]. We implemented the described method on $\rho(T)$ data obtained from GROMACS energy (edr) files. To reduce the effect of density fluctuations, we applied binned averaging to the data with a bin size of 10 K before the tangent fitting. An example of the method can be seen in Figure 4.1.

When utilizing the described methodology for T_g prediction, the slopes of the tangents fitted to the high temperature region varied slightly with cooling rate. Specifically, derivatives in the high temperature region took on smaller (negative) values when increasing cooling rate. This impacted the intersection, and consequently the T_g estimate as well. The glass transition temperatures calculated this way had often an inverse relationship with the quench rate and this behavior was deemed suspicious. The glass transition for each cooling rate was thus decided to be calculated with the high T tangent fixed to the one obtained for the slowest quench. This change made the T_g estimates follow the expected quench rate relationship and the WLF extrapolated laboratory predictions (explained further below) were also of sensible magnitude. A more elaborate motivation for this high temperature tangent fixing can be found in section 5.1 (methodological results).

A second methodological complication stemmed from the high quench rates re-

Figure 4.1: Example of the tangent fit method used to estimate the glass transition T_g from MD quenches.

sulting in a broadening of the transition region. This is observed as a gradual change in the derivative of $\rho(T)$ data in the vicinity of the T_g . The broadening meant that it was not clear whether the tangents were fitted to asymptotic linear regions to begin with. As expected, higher quench rates in the simulations resulted in broader transition region widths. To obtain an unbiased measure of the transition region width, a method developed by Patrone et al. [32] was utilized. The idea was to fit a hyperbolic function $h_\rho(T)$ to the $\rho(T)$ data and then use its derivative to identify the transition regions. The approach eliminated case-by-case identification of the asymptotic regions, reduced the need for input by the modeler, and as such increased reproducibility of the T_g estimates. The functional form of the hyperbola was defined as follows:

$$h_\rho(T) = \rho_0 - a(T - T_0) - b\mathcal{H}(T; T_0, c) \quad (4.1)$$

$$\mathcal{H}(T; T_0, c) = \frac{1}{2}(T - T_0) + \sqrt{\frac{(T - T_0)^2}{4} + e^c} \quad (4.2)$$

The parameters T_0 , ρ_0 , a , b and c can be given simple interpretations. The T_0 and ρ_0 parameters together determine the hyperbola center. The parameters a and b determine the asymptotic slopes for the low and high T regions, given by $-a$ and $-(a + b)$ respectively. The c parameter dictates the sharpness of the glass transition, so that a value approaching $-\infty$ turns the hyperbola into two separate tangents and

larger values make the transition increasingly gradual. The derivative of the $h_\rho(T)$ fit allowed us to express how the slope of $\rho(T)$ changed as a function of temperature. As we wanted the tangents to be fitted to the asymptotic regions, we defined the glass transition region as the region where the $h_\rho(T)$ derivative differed by more than a specific user defined parameter δ from the asymptotic values $-a$ and $-(a+b)$, which we defined to be $\delta = 10\%$. Based on visual inspection, we also introduced cut-off values to the fitting regions to be sure we did not fit the tangents to the transition regions. We set the cut-off to ± 150 K from both ends of the temperature range. In other words, the maximum fitting range could be 100–250 K and 550–700 K at the low and high temperature regions, respectively. An example of the transition region identification is given in Figures 4.2 and 4.3. If it turned out that the data for a certain quench was insufficient (i.e. asymptotic regions were missing), that simulation would be set aside for further analysis or be disregarded completely. As the T_g estimates were quite sensitive to the chosen fitting range, the transition identification scheme made our T_g predictions far less ambiguous, as it constrained the possible fitting ranges.

Figure 4.2: Example of a hyperbolic fit to density-temperature data for a PHBV-glucose system at 2 % loading, together with the identified transition region. The tangents used for T_g estimation should be fitted to the linear regions at both ends of the temperature interval.

An average simulated T_g and its standard deviation σ_g were then calculated from the five parallel simulations for each quench rate q . To relate the different time scales between experiments (~ 10 K/min) and the simulations ($\sim 10^{11}$ - 10^{13} K/min), we

Figure 4.3: Example of the derivative of the fitted hyperbola used to identify the transition regions.

utilized the William-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation [33]. It is equivalent to the VFT equation introduced in section 2.1, and has the following form:

$$T_g(q) = \frac{-C_2 \log_{10}(q_{\text{lab}}/q)}{C_1 + \log_{10}(q_{\text{lab}}/q)} + T_{g,\text{lab}} \quad (4.3)$$

The WLF equation was fitted to simulation data $T_g(q)$ and then the fitted parameter $T_{g,\text{lab}}$ was used as an estimate of the value at the chosen laboratory cooling rate. This procedure had been used successfully in a previous MD study by Soldara et al. [33]. An example of the WLF extrapolation can be seen in Figure 4.4. The laboratory quench rate q_{lab} was set to the constant value of 10 K/min. In accordance with the recommendation by Angel et al. [16] we also fixed the near constant parameter C_1 to a value of 16, in order to increase the stability of the fit. As such, our fitting function contained two free parameters, C_2 and $T_{g,\text{lab}}$, to be determined from the data. The optimal fitting parameters for the WLF equation were then obtained with the least squares fitting approach using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm implemented in the Python lmfit module [34]. The inverse of the standard deviation σ_g for each simulated T_g was used as a weight for the fitting algorithm. The confidence intervals for each fitted parameter were obtained with the F-test.

Chain and additive diffusivities were also analyzed for all systems with 2, 6 and 10 % additive loading based on the trajectories from the isothermal simulations at

Figure 4.4: Left: simulated T_g values at different cooling rates for a PHBV-glucose system at 4 % glucose loading, together with the fitted WLF curve. The error bars are shown with one standard deviation. Right: zoom out of the same fit, showing the extrapolated laboratory T_g obtained from the WLF fit for the cooling rate 10 K/min.

370 K (above T_g). The mean-squared displacements (MSD) of the polymer repeat units as well as the additives were recorded as a function of time for the last 400 ns of each simulation. Reduced chain mobility was taken as a direct indicator of an immobilizing effect due to the additives, and it also allowed for a comparison with the glass transition predictions. Chain mobility was also compared to additive mobility. It was possible to obtain diffusion rate estimates from the MSD curves, but the mobility analyses were decided to be reported simply based on a comparison of the MSDs.

4.2 Hydrogen bond analysis

Previous research had shown a reduction in PHBV secondary crystallization due to saccharide additives, which has been attributed to hydrogen bonding between the polymer chains and additives (Jenkins et al [7]). To test this proposal, hydrogen bond analysis was performed for each additive system for the loadings 2, 6 and 10 % based on trajectories from the 800 ns isothermal (370 K) simulations. Hydrogen bonds between additives, within additives as well as between polymer chains and additives were

identified using the MDAnalysis software [35]. The geometric criterion for a hydrogen bond was a donor-acceptor distance below 3.5 Å and a donor-hydrogen-acceptor angle above 150°.

Figure 4.5: Schematic of a glucose molecule bonded with three hydrogen bonds (shown in yellow) to adjacent PHBV chain segments. The visualization was done with the VMD software [36]. The donor-acceptor distance has to be below 3.5 Å and the donor-hydrogen-acceptor angle above 150° for a hydrogen bond to be identified.

We decided to look at the number of bridging configurations, inter-additive hydrogen bonds and intra-additive hydrogen bonds. Bridging configurations refer in this context to an additive forming hydrogen bonds with two or more adjacent PHBV chains, or with two or more non-consecutive repeat units of a single chain. The hypothesis was that these configurations could reduce chain mobility, and if so, it would show up as changes in glass transition values as well as chain diffusivity. The inter-additive hydrogen bonds allowed us to look for additive clustering. Additive clustering was taken as a possible indication that phase separation could occur over larger time scales, something that could be detrimental to the material properties. However, phase separation could not be directly observed due to time scale limitations of the MD method. The analysis also allowed us to see whether changes in bridging configurations could be attributed to increases or decreases in inter-additive interactions. Finally, intra-additive hydrogen bond analysis allowed us to see whether changes in bridging configurations and/or inter-additive interactions could be attributed to increases or decreases in additive self-interactions. For instance, a tendency to form intra-additive hydrogen bonds could affect the bridging efficiency because donors would be used for additive self-interactions instead. It could also be an indicator of

structural flexibility, which would allow the hydroxy groups within the additive to interact. The hydrogen bonding results were compared to the glass transition and diffusivity results to see whether correlations exist, and if so, they would allow for a better mechanistic understanding of changes in chain dynamics due to additives.

5. Results and discussion

The chapter is divided into two sections. The first section 5.1 presents the most important findings related to predicting glass transition temperatures from MD data. It also explains the assumptions made when analyzing the additive screening results. The second section 5.2 then presents all results obtained from the additive screening.

5.1 Methodological results

Three methodological complications with the glass transition analysis were identified. The first finding was the quench rate dependence of the slope at high temperatures, which made it difficult to use the tangent fit approach for T_g estimation. The second finding was the broadening of the transition region. It was not *a priori* clear whether MD data contained linear asymptotic regions and thus an algorithm for constraining the fitting range was used. The third complication was related to the WLF equation and its proper use when relating timescales of MD to those of laboratory conditions.

The $\rho(T)$ curves showed a quench rate dependence for the slope in the high temperature region. As can be seen in Figure 5.1, faster quenches resulted in a smaller (negative) slope, and vice versa for slower quenches. The slope would eventually converge to a constant value when reducing the cooling rate enough. This quench rate dependence of the slope in the high temperature region raised concerns about the accuracy of the T_g estimates, as slower quench rates could lead to higher T_g values when using the tangent fit method. We concluded that the fastest quench rates (≥ 150 K/ns) were excessively fast for chain conformations to relax in the available time, thus resulting in flatter $\rho(T)$ curves. Pressure and temperature couplings could also play a role if they were not able to alter the system dynamics fast enough. The rationale behind using the very fastest cooling rates was non other than practical, as the additive screenings were expensive and thus finding the shortest possible simulation with sufficient accuracy was valuable. Clearly, the fastest quench rates impacted prediction accuracy, and as such, they should be used with care in future glass transition studies. As the T_g estimates from all quenches were

still needed for a reliable WLF fit, we estimated the glass transition temperatures with the high temperature tangent fixed to the one obtained for the slowest quench. It was thus assumed that the relevant factor that distinguished between systems, based on the same initial configuration but different cooling rates, was the height (and slope) of the lower tangent, not the relatively small slope perturbation of the high temperature tangent. In other words, the low tangent fit determined the quench rate dependence of the T_g estimate. This change was deemed acceptable as the target was not absolute accuracy for the reported glass transition values, rather the values were used for ranking of systems with different additives and loadings.

Figure 5.1: Temperature-density curves for neat PHBV at three cooling rates. The fastest quench at 600 K/ns (red curve) had a more shallow slope as compared to the slower quenches 60 and 6 K/ns (blue and green curve). When the cooling rate is decreased, the slope eventually converges to a constant value, which is indicated by the black line.

The second methodological finding was related to the broadening of the transition region when using very fast quench rates in MD. As can be seen in Figure 5.2, the faster quench rate had a significantly broader transition compared to the more sharp transition of the slower quench rate. The transition width was also found to be dependent on the type of polymer-additive blend. Especially the lower temperature linear asymptotic region became small for some systems considered. As the cooling rate was decreased, the temperature derivative seemed to approach a non-continuous limit at the glass transition, thus resembling a second-order phase

Figure 5.2: Temperature-density plots for a neat PHBV system, together with the hyperbolic fits. The faster quench rate (150 K/ns) to the left resulted in a wider transition region compared to the slower quench rate (6 K/ns) shown to the right. The hyperbolas allowed us to identify if the data was sufficient for T_g estimation with the bilinear fitting method, and also constrained the otherwise arbitrary fitting ranges.

transition as expected. However, the broad transition region in MD studies can lead to problems with unambiguous T_g prediction. Firstly, calculating T_g from data sets lacking asymptotic linear regions most likely leads to unreliable predictions. In MD studies it is common practice that the T_g is estimated by simply assuming that asymptotic regions really are present [32]. Secondly, inadvertently fitting the tangents partly to the transition regions may skew the predictions. We observed that T_g s obtained with the tangent fit approach were sensitive to the fitting ranges. Thus, having a method that identifies whether data sets are sufficient and also limits the fitting ranges is of importance. This problem was considered in the paper by Patrone et al. [32], where the hyperbolic fitting approach was presented. However, it is also important to acknowledge that the proposed hyperbolic form lacks a clear physical basis. This highlights the need for further improved uncertainty estimates for glass transition temperatures predicted from MD data.

The third methodological finding relates to the robustness of the WLF approach when relating the vastly different time scales between experiment and MD. The fitting procedure had to span a wide range of time scales (~ 13 decades) and the robustness of the WLF form is, to the knowledge of the author, not completely understood in these

Figure 5.3: Estimated T_g s from MD data, together with the WLF fits for PHBV-lactose systems at loadings 2, 6 and 10 %. The left plot shows the crossing behavior observed when all three parameters ($C_1, C_2, T_{g,\text{lab}}$) were free in the WLF equation. The right plot shows how the crossing behavior disappeared as the C_1 parameter was fixed to a value of 16.

extreme cases. The WLF equation has nevertheless been used to relate glass transitions temperatures calculated with MD to those at experimental time scales, leading to a decent agreement with experiment [33]. However, in the present study, we observed that using three free parameters in the WLF equation (4.3) and data involving only seven cooling rates resulted in fitting instabilities and significant uncertainty in the extrapolated values. This had to do with a lack of data compared to the number of free parameters, as well as the non-linear form of the WLF equation. When analyzing the obtained T_g values for systems with the same additive at different additive contents, we observed a crossing of the WLF curves when extrapolating to lower cooling rates. This meant that the order of the direct and extrapolated T_g estimates could be different. This, in and of itself, is not necessarily a problem, as the additive content could affect the kinetic fragility of the polymer-additive blend, that is, the rate at which the relaxation time grows when the system approaches T_g . Fragility is related to the C_2 parameter in the WLF equation and is found to range from 24 K (polypropylene oxide) to 104

K (polyisobutylene) [15]. However, both theoretical considerations and experimental findings have suggested that C_1 should have a value close to ~ 16 [16]. As we observed the fitted C_1 value to fluctuate a lot depending on the additive content and additive considered, we concluded that fitting instabilities were likely at play. This view was also supported by the large uncertainty estimates obtained with three fitting parameters. After fixing the C_1 parameter to 16, the excessive crossing behavior disappeared. Figure 5.3 shows the behavior of the WLF extrapolations before and after the parameter-fixing.

5.2 Additive screening

The results from the additive screening suggested that all the additives, except for ascorbyl palmitate, could to some extent elevate the glass transition temperature of the polymer. Especially ascorbic acid turned out to be a promising T_g increasing additive. However, the glass transition results could not be compared to chain and additive mobility as it turned out to be too slow for a reliable comparison between systems. The hydrogen bond analysis showed that the capacity of an additive to bridge polymer chains correlated with increases in T_g , but the results were not conclusive. Additive clustering also increased with increasing additive content for all the additives. The full-scale screenings were preceded by an analysis of neat PHBV systems containing no additives to set the reference level to compare to. The WLF-extrapolated T_g was 267 ± 3 K for the neat polymer, in good agreement with experimental data (see Table 2.2).

Figure 5.4 shows the WLF-extrapolated T_g as a function of additive content for the monosaccharides. As can be seen, glucose showed a larger effect on the T_g as compared to fructose. An increase of 13 ± 5 K was observed for the highest additive contents. Fructose, on the other hand, did not alter the glass transition temperature significantly, and the small increase could be within the uncertainty of the estimation method. The different effects of the monosaccharides on T_g could be related to fructose having a comparable T_g to pure PHBV. Figure 5.5 shows T_g as a function of additive content for the disaccharides and melezitose. As can be seen, sucrose had an increasing effect of 22 ± 11 K on the T_g for the highest additive content. Lactose similarly elevated the T_g by 16 ± 5 K for the higher additive contents. The jump in T_g between 4 and 6 % was traced to a particular sensitivity of the 4 % data point on the details of the WLF extrapolation. A T_g increasing effect was also observed for melezitose. It increased the T_g by 16 ± 5 K for the highest additive content. The di and trisaccharide additives caused a similar or slightly larger T_g increase than glucose. The glass transition temperatures for all saccharides had an

approximately linear dependence on the additive content. Figure 5.6 shows the T_g as a function of additive content for ascorbic acid and ascorbyl palmitate. As can be seen, ascorbic acid increased the T_g significantly for the higher additive contents, with a 23 ± 5 K increase at 10 % loading. The T_g dependence on additive content was linear, just as for the saccharide additives. Ascorbyl palmitate on the other hand, had a decreasing effect on the T_g , which is indicative of a plasticizing effect.

Figure 5.4: The left plot shows the WLF-extrapolated T_g predictions for glucose as a function of additive content at a cooling rate of 10 K/ns. The same is shown for fructose on the right.

Figure 5.7 shows the T_g as a function of additive content for all additives in the same plot. The T_g value obtained for pure PHBV is shown in gray. As can be seen, the results were of similar magnitude for ascorbic acid, melezitose, the disaccharides and glucose. Fructose had only a minor effect on T_g , if any. Ascorbyl palmitate was the only additive that caused a decrease in the glass transition temperature. The glass transition analysis enabled us to divide the additives into three rough categories based on the aforementioned observations.

Chain and additive mobility were analyzed to determine their respective diffusivities, based on data from the isothermal 370 K simulations. A slowing down of chain mobility would be direct evidence of additives inhibiting chain movement in the amorphous polymer fractions, thus leading to a reduction in secondary crystallization over larger time scales. Figure 5.8 shows the mean-squared displacement (MSD) of

Figure 5.5: The upper left plot shows the WLF-extrapolated T_g predictions for sucrose as a function of additive content at a cooling rate of 10 K/ns. The same is shown for lactose in the upper right plot and for melezitose in the lower plot.

both additives and polymer chains for the additive content 10 %. As can be seen, the MSDs of the repeat units and the additives were closely correlated and also of similar magnitude. This indicated that the additives were effectively trapped between the polymer chains. The MSD magnitudes also corresponded roughly to the length of a 3HB repeat unit over the course of the whole 400 ns simulation, making it difficult

Figure 5.6: The left plot shows the WLF extrapolated T_g predictions for ascorbic acid as a function of additive content at a cooling rate of 10 K/ns. The same is shown for ascorbyl palmitate to the right.

Figure 5.7: WLF-extrapolated T_g predictions as a function of additive content shown for all additives at loadings 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 %. The neat system T_g is also shown in gray for reference.

to distinguish between systems. The diffusion of additives and polymer repeat units thus turned out to be too slow to reliably predict the additive effect on chain mobility.

This was true for all polymer-additive systems considered. Re-running the simulations at a temperature above 370 K was not considered, as it was expected to disrupt the polymer-additive hydrogen bonding. The conclusion was that chain mobility is difficult to access for the kind of systems studied in this work, and as such it could not be used to for formulation ranking. The difficulty ultimately stemmed from the time scale limitation of the MD method.

Figure 5.8: MSD curves for all additives at 10% loading are shown to the left, and similarly for the polymer chains on the right. The colors correspond to the same PHBV-additive system.

Hydrogen bonding patterns, such as physical bridging configurations between chains and additives, and inter and intra-additive bonds, were also analyzed based on the isothermal simulations. Frequency and density of bridging configurations were compared to T_g and diffusivity results to see whether hydrogen bond bridging could be related to increased material stability, in accordance with the study by Jenkins et al [7]). Inter-additive hydrogen bonding, on the other hand, was taken to be an indicator of additive clustering which, in turn, could suggest the possibility of phase separation over larger time scales. Intra-additive hydrogen bonding was also analyzed to see whether differences in the bridging frequency could be explained by additive donors being used for internal bonding instead.

The hydrogen bonding results can be seen in Figures 5.9 and 5.10, as well as in Table 5.1. The right top plot in 5.9 shows the total number of physical cross-links between polymer chains and additives as a function of additive content, whereas the left top plot in Figure 5.9 shows the same thing normalized by donor count.

The plots show that glucose was the most efficient additive at bridging both in absolute and relative terms. It was followed by fructose, ascorbic acid and lactose in no particular order. Ascorbyl palmitate, on the other hand, was the least efficient additive, both in absolute and relative terms. As can be seen in the right top plot of Figure 5.9, the fraction of donors participating in bridging decreased with the additive content. The drop was of order 10-15 % when going from low to higher additive content.

Figure 5.9: Top left: number of physical bridging configurations N_{hb}^{X} . Top right: number of physical bridging configurations N_{hb}^{X} normalized by additive donor count N_{d} . Lower left: number of inter-additive hydrogen bond configurations $N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}^\dagger}$ normalized by additive donor count N_{d} . Lower right: number of intra-additive hydrogen bond configurations $N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}}$ normalized by additive donor count N_{d} . All results are shown as a function of additive content.

The inter-additive hydrogen bonds are shown in the lower left plot of Figure 5.9, normalized by donor count and as a function of additive content. The results showed that ascorbic acid, glucose and melezitose were the most prominent at hydrogen bonding with adjacent additives. Increasing the additive content increased clustering by 10-15 %. This increase thus seemed to fully explain the observed drop

in the bridging efficiency. For all systems considered, the fraction of donors used for additive-additive bonding stayed below 15 %, and, as such, inter-additive hydrogen bonds were significantly less frequent than bridging ones.

The number of intra-additive hydrogen bonds is shown in the lower right plot of Figure 5.9, normalized by donor count and as a function of additive content. The data indicated that intra-additive interactions occurred to some extent for all additives. The disaccharides and melezitose had the most intra-additive interactions, whereas glucose and ascorbic acid had very few. Fructose and ascorbyl palmitate had intra-additive interactions somewhere between, and ascorbyl palmitate was the only additive showing a decreasing self-interaction trend when increasing additive content. The insensitivity of additive self-interactions with respect to additive content seemed reasonable, as internal additive bonding was not expected to depend much on the amount of additive in the system.

Figure 5.10: Left: T_g as a function of physical bridging configurations for each additive at loadings 2, 6 and 10 %. Right: The same plot but the x-axis is shown as bridging concentration, defined as the average bridging configurations in the system normalized by volume.

Figure 5.10 shows the glass transition values for all additives, both as a function of the number of chain bridging hydrogen bond configurations to the left, as well as a function of bridging concentration to the right. The data corresponds to additive contents 2, 6 and 10 %. As can be seen in Figure 5.10, the number of physical bridging configurations in a system correlated somewhat with increases in T_g as was the case for ascorbic acid, the disaccharides and melezitose. However, changes in T_g could not be

completely attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding, even though a correlation existed. For instance, melezitose and sucrose had among the lowest bridging efficiencies in both absolute and relative terms (see Figure 5.9), but were among the best T_g increasing additives. The lower bridging efficiencies observed for the aforementioned additives could be traced to relatively high frequencies of intra and inter-additive bonding. The reason for this may be related to the flexible structure of the larger saccharides that allow the constituent parts to bend and rotate around the glycosidic linkage. The size of the additive also mattered, as bulkier saccharides caused larger elevations in T_g . This pointed at greater steric hindrance being of importance, when searching for suitable additives that can reduce secondary crystallization. However, steric effects were not studied in the present study. Table 5.1 shows a summary of all the obtained hydrogen bond statistics in absolute terms, together with the glass transition predictions.

Additive	w (%)	T_g (K)	$\pm\sigma_1$ (K)	N_{hb}^X	$\pm\sigma_1$	$N_{hb}^{AA\dagger}$	$\pm\sigma_1$	N_{hb}^{AA}	$\pm\sigma_1$
Neat	0	267	3						
Glucose	2	273	1	216	13	13	3	4	2
	4	275	2						
	6	274	2	542	21	121	7	12	4
	8	280	2						
	10	279	2	789	26	323	13	17	4
Fructose	2	266	3	185	12	8	2	23	4
	4	271	2						
	6	275	4	490	21	103	8	67	7
	8	268	3						
	10	273	3	744	26	227	11	111	8
Sucrose	2	267	6	150	9	10	3	42	5
	4	276	4						
	6	280	4	399	15	68	5	131	8
	8	276	5						
	10	289	8	562	20	240	11	205	10
Lactose	2	267	7	161	9	11	2	33	5
	4	265	3						
	6	281	2	427	16	80	6	99	7
	8	283	3						
	10	283	3	631	19	218	10	156	10
Melezitose	2	269	3	138	8	12	2	39	5
	4	271	3						
	6	278	3	367	14	83	6	103	7
	8	277	7						
	10	283	2	528	16	250	11	172	10

Additive	w (%)	T_g (K)	$\pm\sigma_1$ (K)	N_{hb}^X	$\pm\sigma_1$	$N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}\dagger}$	$\pm\sigma_1$	$N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}}$	$\pm\sigma_1$
Asc. acid	2	267	2	164	12	12	2	1	1
	4	266	5						
	6	279	8	405	18	126	7	3	1
	8	282	5						
	10	290	3	581	22	281	11	4	2
Asc. palm.	2	261	3	46	7	0	0	10	2
	4	265	9						
	6	260	7	116	11	18	3	26	4
	8	252	9						
	10	263	6	186	16	42	4	35	5

Table 5.1: Glass transition and hydrogen bonding results for glucose and fructose at different additive contents, together with uncertainties given with one standard deviation. The first result column shows the T_g results, the second shows the number of physical bridging configurations N_{hb}^X , the third shows the number of inter-additive hydrogen bonds $N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}\dagger}$, and the last column shows the number of intra-additive hydrogen bonds $N_{\text{hb}}^{\text{AA}}$.

6. Conclusions

Molecular simulations of PHBV systems containing different additives at different loadings were performed to determine whether a group of pre-selected, non-toxic and biobased additives could reduce the rate of secondary crystallization and thus physical aging in PHBV. As secondary crystallization could not be directly investigated, an increase in T_g and a reduction in polymer chain mobility were the foremost indicators of a stabilizing additive effect. The rationale was that elevating the T_g above room temperature would inhibit the mobility of the amorphous fractions, thus preventing the polymer properties from changing over time. As previous research had attributed a decrease in secondary crystallization to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the polymer chains and the additives, hydrogen bonding patterns in the systems were analyzed to test this hypothesis that physical hydrogen bond bridging can increase material stability.

The results from the molecular simulations suggested that all additives, except for ascorbyl palmitate, could to some extent elevate the glass transition temperature of PHBV. The elevation was dependent on the additive content as well as the additive type. All T_g elevating additives seemed to have linearly increasing T_g trends when increasing additive loading. The most potent T_g increasing agent was ascorbic acid, followed by melezitose, the disaccharides and glucose in no particular order. We suggest that follow-up studies should investigate even higher additive contents than considered in the present study for the aforementioned additives. We also observed a clear T_g decreasing effect of ascorbyl palmitate, and as such, it was not considered a secondary crystallization inhibitor. Fructose, on the other hand, did not seem to alter the T_g in any direction. The T_g results could not be compared to above- T_g chain and additive mobility due to the time scale limitations of the simulations. The number of chain-bridging hydrogen bond configurations was found to correlate with increases in T_g , but the data was not totally conclusive. The inter-additive hydrogen bonding patterns also revealed that clustering was taking place for all additives and it increased with the loading. This could be of concern regarding phase separation, which may degrade material properties over larger time

scales. In the search for new PHBV-additive formulations, the results indicated that additives with many hydrogen bond donors and larger sizes are best suited to increase the T_g . Using additives with long but flexible side chains containing no interacting groups (as for ascorbyl palmitate) seemed to be a T_g decreasing design. The data also suggested that steric effects were important, as bulkier additives in general seemed to result in higher T_g values. Thus, the results from the MD simulations supported the conclusions of the experimental studies presented in chapter 2.3.

Due to uncertainties arising from the MD method, the results should not be considered as absolute predictions, but rather as indicators suitable for ranking purposes. The largest uncertainties ultimately stemmed from time scale limitations of the MD method, as well as accuracy limitations of the available force fields. As such, methodological complications were identified related to the very fast quench rates needed in MD simulations. The dependence of thermal expansivity on the quench rate in the high temperature limit suggested that future glass transition analyses should use cooling rates as slow as reasonably possible, in order to increase the accuracy of the prediction. Data sets should also first and foremost contain linear regions if the tangent fit method is to be used, and if so, the fitting ranges should be restricted to these regions only. Thus, a good algorithm for asymptotic region identification is of importance for consistent results. The different time scales between simulation and experiment were taken into account with the WLF equation that allowed us to predict T_g values extrapolated to laboratory settings. This refers to cooling rates relevant for polymer melt processing. The WLF fit sensitivity was checked thoroughly, and the conclusion was that a free fit to only six or seven data points was too unstable for reliable parameter estimates. This motivated us to fix the C_1 parameter to its so-called universal value in accordance with the conclusions of Angel et al. [16]. This reduced fitting instabilities and thus improved the glass transition predictions.

The methodology presented in this thesis shows potential in the search for additives that could reduce secondary crystallization in PHBV and other polyesters. However, methodological refinements are still needed if the presented methods are to be used on an even larger scale. Especially, the sensitivity of the glass transition predictions on user input has to be further minimized in future studies. The lifetime of the bridging hydrogen bond configurations could also have been studied to obtain an indication of their stability. Nevertheless, with minor refinements such as the ones suggested above, the results indicated that similar methods could be used on an even larger scale, both in academia and industry, to accelerate the transition from fossil-based plastics to more environmentally friendly alternatives.

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